

MULTIVARIABLE OPTIMISATION OF FIBRE REINFORCED HONEYCOMB SANDWICH PANELS

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1. Introduction

Sandwich construction, consisting of strong, stiff facings bonded to a relatively thick, low density core, is common in many structural applications of polymer composites. A wide variety of core materials (aluminium, Kevlar, polypropylene, etc.) are available, each having its own advantages and disadvantages. In a recent article, a relatively novel concept using short fibres as reinforcement in the cell walls of the honeycomb cores has been reported in Rao. et.al [1], the cores are not only structurally viable but also provide the advantage of being reprocessed. Several other properties such as energy absorption due to impact loading, sound absorption etc. are reported in [2-4].

Typically, sandwich panels are used in flexural applications where they behave similar to I-beam, where the facings sustain the bending stresses and the core takes the shear. Using a weak core assumption [5], common failures observed in panels under such loading may be faceplate fracture, shear failure of the core, wrinkling of the faceplate into the core or outwards due to delamination at their interface, and each of which can be determined by testing them individually. The results from these simplified tests will be helpful in setting failure criteria or stress constraints for sandwich panels as a whole during the design stage. For example, faceplate wrinkling in a sandwich panel can be avoided by designing a faceplate to withstand wrinkling stresses by considering it to be subjected to compressive edge loading and assuming one side of it to be resting on infinite elastic medium [6,7]. The buckling load during testing will give an indication of the maximum stress at which the faceplates would start to wrinkle, and by setting this critical stress as a failure criterion for faceplate wrinkling, the sandwich panel could be designed

against that failure mode. Similarly, to avoid face dimpling into the core, the face dimpling or the intercellular buckling stress is calculated by using plate buckling theory for the in-plane stresses in the facings at which the face plate buckles at regions that are unsupported by the cell walls [8]. By using these simplified tests, failure criteria in terms of mathematical equations are setup and analytical solutions [9] for the whole panel are developed which in essence would reduce experimentation.

In this paper, failure maps have been constructed for various relative densities of the core, considering six failure criteria when the beam is subjected to four-point bending loads (quarter-span). Aluminium (5052-H34 alloy), was chosen as the facesheet material for the sake of simplicity and solutions were obtained for isotropic and specially orthotropic core materials. The optimum weight and hence the cost of the sandwich beam was obtained at the confluence of any four of these failure criterion considered in the four parameter optimisation.

2. Materials

Unreinforced and reinforced polypropylene was considered as a core material. Reinforcements consisted of synthetic and natural fibres. Properties of fibre reinforced core materials were calculated using the rule-of-mixtures method. All core material costs were from [10], and were converted using foreign currency rates obtained on 15/03/2012.

Table 1 Foreign currency conversion rates

	USD	EUR	GBP
NZD	0.81	0.62	0.51
Inverse	1.24	1.61	1.93

Table 2 Properties of polypropylene (from [10])

Density, ρ [kg/m ³]	900
Modulus of elasticity, E [GPa]	1.4
Poisson's ratio, ν	0.33
Shear strength, τ_s [MPa]	16.5
Cost [NZD/kg] (from [9])	1.61 – 2.25

Table 3 Properties of natural reinforcing fibres [10,11,12]

	Flax	Hemp	Jute	Kenaf	Sisal
ρ [kg/m ³]	1500	1470	1300	1450	1500
E [GPa]	27.6	70	26.5	53	9.4 – 22
ν	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.17
Cost [NZD/kg]	0.48 – 2.09	0.48 – 1.61	0.81 – 1.13	0.64 – 2.42	0.81 – 1.29

Table 4 Properties of synthetic reinforcing fibres [10-14]

	Carbon	E-glass
ρ [kg/m ³]	1400	2500
E [GPa]	235	70
ν	0.27	0.24
Cost [NZD/kg]	16.10 – 32.20	1.45 – 2.58

3. Failure Criteria

Six failure criteria have been considered in the analysis of a sandwich beam under four-point bending (quarter-span) as shown in Figure 1. Unless otherwise stated, it is assumed that the facesheets are much thinner and stiffer than the core ($t_f/t_c \leq 0.1, E_f/E_c \geq$).

Figure 1 Schematic of sandwich beam under four-point (quarter-span) bending

3.1 Non-dimensional parameters

Five non-dimensional parameters were obtained using a method outlined by White [15] to relate a failure load index of the beam to several geometric parameters. These parameters are outlined below.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Load index, } \Pi_1 &= \frac{P_{cr}}{LE_f} \\ \Pi_2 &= \frac{t_f}{L} \\ \Pi_3 &= \frac{t_c}{L} \\ \Pi_4 &= \frac{t_{cell}}{L} \\ \Pi_5 &= \frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \end{aligned} \quad (3.1)$$

Additionally, a weight index to be used as an objective function for the optimisation routine was also defined.

$$w = 2\rho_f\Pi_2 + \rho_s\Pi_3\Pi_5 \text{ [kgm}^{-3}\text{]} \quad (3.2)$$

A cost index can also be defined and used as an alternative objective function for the optimisation routine.

$$c = 2c_f\rho_f\Pi_2 + c_s\rho_s\Pi_3\Pi_5 \text{ [\$m}^{-3}\text{]} \quad (3.3)$$

3.2 Facesheet cracking (FC)

The normal stress generated in the facesheets under four-point bending (quarter span) is provided in equation (3.4).

$$\sigma = \frac{P(L - L_1)}{2t_f(t_f + t_c)} \approx \frac{P(L - L_1)}{2t_ft_c} \quad (3.4)$$

Since quarter span bending is considered, $L_1 = L/2$. Thus, the failure load of the beam, P_{cr} , can be shown to be:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{4\sigma_{f,cr}(t_f t_c)}{L} \quad (3.5)$$

This equation can then be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional parameters as shown in equation (3.6). Failure will not occur as long as the inequality is satisfied.

$$\frac{1}{4}\Pi_1 \left(\frac{E_f}{\sigma_{f,cr}} \right) (\Pi_2 \Pi_3)^{-1} \leq 1 \quad (3.6)$$

3.3 Facesheet wrinkling

The stress at which facesheet wrinkling occurs, obtained using the following equation, is given by Triantafillou and Gibson [16].

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{FW} &= B_1 E_{f,x}^{1/3} E_3^{2/3}, B_1 \\ &= \frac{3}{(12(3 - \nu_{c,xz})^2 (1 + \nu_{c,xz})^2)^{1/3}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

In this case, $\nu_{c,xz} \approx \nu_s$, and the out-of-plane modulus, E_3 , can be related to the modulus of the cell wall material using:

$$E_3 = \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right) E_s \quad (3.8)$$

Note that for isotropic materials, $E_s = E$, while for specially orthotropic materials, $E_s = E_L$, where E_L is the longitudinal modulus of the cell wall material, assuming that the fibres are oriented parallel to the 3-direction of the core.

Using the equation (3.4), the failure load of the beam is provided below.

$$P_{cr} = \frac{4B_1}{L} E_f^{1/3} \left(\left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right) E_s \right)^{2/3} (t_f t_c) \quad (3.9)$$

This failure criterion can then be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional parameters as:

$$\frac{1}{4}\Pi_1 B_1^{-1} \Pi_5^{-2/3} \left(\frac{E_s}{E_f} \right)^{-2/3} (\Pi_2 \Pi_3)^{-1} \leq 1 \quad (3.10)$$

3.4 Intracellular buckling

The stress at which intracellular buckling occurs is given in the following equation, obtained from Petras [3].

$$\sigma_{IB} = \frac{8E_f t_f^2}{S^2(1 - \nu_f^2)} \quad (3.11)$$

Substituting the intracellular buckling stress into equation (3.4) yields:

$$\frac{P(L - L_1)}{2t_f t_c} = \frac{8E_f t_f^2}{S^2(1 - \nu_f^2)} \quad (3.12)$$

The cell diameter, S , is able to be expressed as a function of the relative density of the core and cell wall thickness.

$$S = \frac{8t_{cell}}{3} \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.13)$$

Thus, the failure load of the beam for this particular mode can be shown to be:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{32E_f(t_f^3 t_c)}{L \left(\frac{8t_{cell}}{3} \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^{-1} \right)^2 (1 - \nu_f^2)} \quad (3.14)$$

This failure criterion can then be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional parameters as:

$$\frac{2\Pi_1 \Pi_4^2 (1 - \nu_f^2)}{9\Pi_5^2 (\Pi_2 \Pi_3)} \leq 1 \quad (3.15)$$

3.5 Cell wall shear yielding (CY)

Considering a unit cell section of the honeycomb core, the average shear stress acting on the section is given by:

$$\tau_{xz,avg} = \frac{P}{t_f + t_c} \approx \frac{P}{t_c} \quad (3.16)$$

Considering force equilibrium in the ribbon direction, the average shear stress in the core can be expressed in terms of the shear stress in a single cell wall, as shown in equation (3.17).

$$\tau_{xz,avg} = \frac{P}{t_c} = \frac{3}{4} \tau_{cell} \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right) \quad (3.17)$$

Cell wall shear yielding occurs when the shear stress in an individual cell wall exceeds the shear strength of the cell wall material. Thus, the failure load of the beam for this failure mode is given by:

$$P_{cr} = \frac{3}{4} \tau_s \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right) t_c \quad (3.18)$$

This failure criterion can be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional parameters as:

$$\frac{4\Pi_1 E_f}{3\Pi_3\Pi_5 \tau_s} \leq 1 \quad (3.19)$$

3.6 Cell wall buckling (CB)

(a) Isotropic material

The in-plane shear load at which a cell wall undergoes buckling is given by Euler's formula for elastic buckling of a plate under shear.

$$\tau_{cell} = \frac{K\pi^2 E}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{t_{cell}}{l_{cell}} \right)^2 \quad (3.20)$$

The relative density of the core can be expressed as a function of the thickness to length ratio of the cell walls using equation (3.21).

$$\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} = \frac{8}{3\sqrt{3}} \left(\frac{t_{cell}}{l_{cell}} \right) \quad (3.21)$$

Using the equation (3.17), the failure load for this particular mode can be shown to be:

$$P_{cr} = \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^4 \frac{K\pi^2 E_s}{12(1-\nu^2)} \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^3 t_c \quad (3.22)$$

This failure criterion can then be expressed in terms of the non-dimensional parameters as shown in equation (3.23).

$$\frac{\Pi_1 E_s L^2 \Pi_4^2 \Pi_5}{7.112 M \Pi_2 (2\Pi_2 + \Pi_3)} \leq 1 \quad (3.23)$$

The shear buckling parameter, $K = 5.35$, if we assume the cell walls to be simply supported.

(b) Specially orthotropic

A method for calculating the shear buckling load of a simply supported orthotropic plate has been presented by Leissa [17], using results from Fogg [18]. This method uses two non-dimensional parameters, provided in equation (3.24), to calculate the value of the shear buckling parameter, provided in equation (3.25).

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &= \frac{\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}{D_{12} + 2D_{66}}; B \\ &= \frac{l_{cell}}{t_c} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \right)^{1/4} \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} k_s &= (3.32 + 2.17(1/\theta) \\ &\quad - 0.163(1/\theta)^2) \\ &\quad + B^2(1.54 \\ &\quad + 2.36(1/\theta) \\ &\quad + 0.1(1/\theta)^2) \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

The shear load in an individual cell wall at which buckling occurs can then be calculated with equation (3.26), while the failure load of the beam in this mode is given in equation (3.27).

$$\tau_{xy}^* = \frac{k_s \pi^2 \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}^3}}{t_{cell} l_{cell}^2} \quad (3.26)$$

$$P_{cr} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \frac{k_s \pi^2 \sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}^3}}{l_{cell}^3} t_c \quad (3.27)$$

The equation for the shear buckling parameter can be substituted into equation (3.27), and the overall equation simplified by separating the non-dimensional geometric parameters from the material properties to obtain equations (3.28) and (3.29).

Note that the non-dimensional parameter θ from equation (3.24) has been redefined.

$$P_{cr} = \left(\frac{27\pi^2}{1024} \right) (Q_{11}Q_{22}^3)^{1/4} \left(A \left(\frac{t_c}{L} \right) \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^3 + C \left(\frac{t_c}{L} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{t_{cell}}{L} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right) \right) L \quad (3.28)$$

$$\Pi_1 \left(\frac{27\pi^2}{1024} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{(Q_{11}Q_{22}^3)^{1/4}}{E_f} \right)^{-1} (A\Pi_3\Pi_5^3 + C\Pi_3^{-1}\Pi_4^2\Pi_5)^{-1} \leq 1$$

Where:

$$A = 3.32 + 2.17(1/\theta) - 0.163(1/\theta)^2 \quad (3.29)$$

$$C = \frac{64}{27} \sqrt{\frac{Q_{11}}{Q_{22}}} (1.54 + 2.36(1/\theta) + 0.1(1/\theta)^2)$$

$$\theta = \frac{\sqrt{Q_{11}Q_{22}}}{Q_{12} + 2Q_{66}}$$

4. Optimisation procedure

The optimum weight of the sandwich beam can be obtained at the confluence of any four failure criterion in a four parameter optimisation. This optimisation method is similar to that used by Banerjee and Bhattacharyya [9], where a three-parameter optimisation was performed and the optimum weight was obtained at the confluence of three failure criterion.

As there are five failure criteria in total, there are five different combinations of four failure criterion which need to be evaluated to obtain five optimal weight values, of which one is the global optimum. The five combinations to be evaluated are summarised in Table 5, with the equations describing the different failure modes summarised in Equation (3.30).

Detailed explanation of all the combinations is presented elsewhere [19] Note that for certain combinations, extra variables are defined to make the equations clearer. These extra defined variables may be found in more than one combination, but their definition only applies to the specific combination in which they are defined.

Table 5 Combinations of failure criteria used to obtain optimal parameters

1. FC-FW-IB-CY	2. FC-FW-IB-CB	3. FC-FW-CY-CB	4. FC-IB-CY-CB	5. FW-IB-CY-CB
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$$\frac{1}{4} \Pi_1 \left(\frac{E_f}{\sigma_{f,cr}} \right) (\Pi_2\Pi_3)^{-1} \leq 1 \text{ (FC)}$$

$$\frac{1}{4} \Pi_1 B_1^{-1} \Pi_5^{-2/3} \left(\frac{E_s}{E_f} \right)^{-2/3} (\Pi_2\Pi_3)^{-1} \leq 1 \text{ (FW)}$$

$$\frac{2\Pi_1\Pi_4^2(1 - \nu_f^2)}{9\Pi_5^2(\Pi_2^3\Pi_3)} \leq 1 \text{ (IB)} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\frac{4\Pi_1 E_f}{3\Pi_3\Pi_5 \tau_s} \leq 1 \text{ (CY)}$$

$$\Pi_1 \left(\frac{27\pi^2}{1024} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{(Q_{11}Q_{22}^3)^{1/4}}{E_f} \right)^{-1} (A\Pi_3 + C\Pi_3^{-1}\Pi_4^2\Pi_5)^{-1} \leq 1 \text{ (CB)}$$

5. Validation of manual four-parameter optimization

In order to establish the validity of the manual four-parameter optimisation method, results obtained from the manual optimisation are compared with results obtained using the MATLAB optimisation toolbox with the appropriate constraints (i.e. only four failure criterion modelled at a time) for the case of a sandwich beam with a polypropylene core and aluminium facesheets and a desired load index of 1×10^{-8} .

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Table 6 manual optimisation for a load index of 1×10^{-8}

Combination	w	Π_2	Π_3	Π_4	Π_5
FC-FW-IB-CY	1.7630	3.1938×10^{-4}	2.1004×10^{-3}	1.5899×10^{-4}	2.7047×10^{-2}
FC-FW-IB-CB	0.6168	4.1279×10^{-5}	1.6251×10^{-2}	2.0549×10^{-5}	2.7047×10^{-2}
FC-FW-CY-CB	1.7630	3.1938×10^{-4}	2.1004×10^{-3}	1.1077×10^{-4}	2.7047×10^{-2}
FC-IB-CY-CB	1.5763	2.8455×10^{-4}	2.3574×10^{-3}	1.2620×10^{-4}	2.4098×10^{-2}
FW-IB-CY-CB	1.6685	3.0176×10^{-4}	2.4902×10^{-3}	1.3410×10^{-4}	2.2813×10^{-2}

Once the four optimal parameters have been determined, the parameters are used to evaluate all five failure criterion to establish the feasibility of the solution.

Table 7 Failure criterion for manual optimisation for a load index of 1×10^{-8}

Combination	FC	FW	IB	CY	CB	Feasible?
FC-FW-IB-CY	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.5199	Yes
FC-FW-IB-CB	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	0.1293	1.0000	Yes
FC-FW-CY-CB	1.0000	1.0000	0.4854	1.0000	1.0000	Yes
FC-IB-CY-CB	1.0000	1.0800	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	No
FW-IB-CY-CB	0.8927	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	Yes

From Table 6 and Table 7 it can be seen that the second combination provides the global optimum for this particular load index and material configuration as the lowest weight index is obtained along with the five failure criterion being satisfied.

The bounds and starting points for the optimisation procedure are provided in Table 8 below.

Table 8 Bounds and starting point for validation of manual optimisation procedure

Parameter	Lower bound	Upper bound	Starting point
Π_2	1×10^{-6}	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-4}
Π_3	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-1}	1×10^{-3}
Π_4	1×10^{-6}	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-4}
Π_5	1×10^{-4}	1×10^0	1×10^{-2}

Results from this validation for the manual optimisation method using MATLAB are provided in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9 Results from validation of manual optimisation for a load index of 1×10^{-8}

Combination	w	Π_2	Π_3	Π_4	Π_5
FC-FW-IB-CY	0.3805	4.2931×10^{-5}	1.0000×10^{-1}	1.5833×10^{-6}	1.6705×10^{-3}
FC-FW-IB-CB	0.6143	4.6672×10^{-5}	1.4373×10^{-2}	2.4184×10^{-5}	2.8154×10^{-2}
FC-FW-CY-CB	0.3805	4.2930×10^{-5}	1.0000×10^{-1}	4.5086×10^{-3}	1.6706×10^{-3}
FC-IB-CY-CB	0.6143	4.6672×10^{-5}	1.4373×10^{-2}	2.4184×10^{-5}	2.8154×10^{-2}
FW-IB-CY-CB	0.6030	5.2514×10^{-5}	1.1948×10^{-2}	2.7948×10^{-5}	2.9897×10^{-2}

Table 10 Failure criterion for validation of manual optimisation for a load index of 1×10^{-8}

Combination	FC	FW	IB	CY	CB	Feasible?
FC-FW-IB-CY	0.1562	1.0000	0.2248	0.3401	692.3	No
FC-FW-IB-CB	1.0000	0.9736	1.0000	0.1404	1.0000	Yes
FC-FW-CY-CB	0.1563	1.0000	1.8230×10^6	0.3400	0.5336	No

FC-IB- CY-CB	1.0000	0.9736	1.0000	0.1404	1.0000	Yes
FW-IB- CY-CB	1.0691	1.0000	1.0000	0.1590	1.0000	No

From the results of the MATLAB validation of the manual four-parameter optimisation, it can be seen that the second and fourth combinations provide the same feasible optimal solution. The values of the parameters in the second combination closely match those obtained with the manual method. There are significant discrepancies in the values of the parameters between both optimisation methods for all other combinations.

5.1 MATLAB four-parameter optimization

In order to obtain the global minimum using a MATLAB routine, all five failure criterion were considered at once. The ‘fmincon’ function in the MATLAB Optimization Toolbox was used. This function finds the minimum of a constrained nonlinear multivariable function, in the form shown below

$$\min_x f(x) \text{ such that } \begin{cases} c(x) \leq 0 \\ ceq(x) = 0 \\ A \cdot x \leq b \\ Aeq \cdot x = beq \\ lb \leq x \leq ub \end{cases}$$

x is the vector of variables, with A, Aeq, b and beq used to define linear equality and inequality constraints. c and ceq are used to define nonlinear inequality and equality constraints respectively, with lb and ub defining the lower and upper bounds respectively.

Within the ‘fmincon’ function, the active-set algorithm is used. This algorithm is used for general nonlinear optimisation, and uses a sequential quadratic programming (SQP) method.

In addition to the five failure criterion, a sixth criterion, to ensure the correct facesheet to core thickness ratio was also implemented. The bounds and starting point of the optimisation routine are provided in Table 8. Results from this optimisation

for the case as described earlier are provided in Table 11 and Table 12.

Table 11 MATLAB optimisation in terms of load indices

w	Π_2	Π_3	Π_4	Π_5
0.6143	4.6672×10^{-5}	1.4373×10^{-2}	2.4184×10^{-5}	2.8154×10^{-2}

Table 12 MATLAB optimisation in terms of failure criteria

FC	FW	IB	CY	CB	t_f/t_c
1.0000	0.9736	1.0000	0.1404	1.0000	0.0032

Figure 2 Visualisation of failure modes from optimal parameters obtained using manual optimisation procedure and MATLAB routine

It can be seen that the results obtained from the manual and MATLAB optimisation routines are similar. This is confirmed by examination of the

optimal parameters generated using both methods. There is some slight variation between the two results, as shown in Table 13.

Table 13 manual and MATLAB optimisation results comparison

	w	Π_2	Π_3	Π_4	Π_5
$\left(\frac{\text{MATLAB-Manual}}{\text{Manual}}\right) \times 100\%$	-0.4	13.06	-11.56	17.69	4.09

6. Results and discussion

Results from the manual optimisation procedure and MATLAB routine were obtained for the case of a sandwich beam with an aluminium facesheet and polypropylene honeycomb core. The optimal weight index was determined for a range of load indices from 1×10^{-8} to 1×10^{-6} . This load index range corresponds to a load (per unit width) between 703 N/m and 70300 N/m, assuming a beam with a span of 1m

From Figure 3, it can be seen that the optimal weight index predicted by both the manual procedure and MATLAB routine are similar at load indices of 1×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-6} . Between a load index of 1×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-7} , the optimal weight index predicted by the manual procedure diverges from the result obtained using MATLAB, before converging between a load index of 1×10^{-7} and 1×10^{-6} .

From the plot of the optimal parameters versus load index in Figure 3, it can be seen that the parameters obtained from the manual optimisation procedure and MATLAB routine are similar at load indices of 1×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-6} . A large step can be observed in the results obtained using the manual optimisation procedure at a load index slightly below 1×10^{-7} , while the trend from the MATLAB routine is continuous for all parameters. It can also be seen that the results for parameter Π_5 , representing the relative density of the core, are similar for both optimisation procedures from a load index slightly under 1×10^{-7} to 1×10^{-6} .

Figure 3 Comparison of weight index vs. load index for manual optimisation and MATLAB routine (L); Comparison of optimal geometric parameters obtained using manual optimisation and MATLAB routine (note that the solid lines represent results obtained from the man

Examination of the dominant failure combination from the manual procedure shows that for load indices below 7.6×10^{-8} , combination two is the dominant failure mode combination, while combination four is dominant for load indices greater than and equal to 7.6×10^{-8} . This transition between dominant failure mode combinations corresponds to the sharp kink seen in the plot of the optimal weight index versus load index for the manual procedure.

7. Summary

In this work, fibre reinforced honeycomb core sandwich panels when subjected to four-point bending loads (quarter-span) has been optimised for weight considering six failure criteria. Aluminium (5052-H34 alloy), was chosen as the facesheet material for the sake of simplicity and solutions were obtained for isotropic and specially orthotropic core materials. The optimum weight and hence the cost of the sandwich beam was obtained at the confluence of any four of these failure criterion considered in the four parameter optimisation.

From the results of the MATLAB validation of the manual four-parameter optimisation, FC-FW-IB-CB and FC-IB-CY-CB combinations provide the same feasible optimal solution. The values of the parameters in FC-FW-IB-CB combination closely match those obtained with the manual method.

However, the optimal weight index comparison, the weight index predicted by both the manual procedure and MATLAB routine were similar at load indices of 1×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-6} , but between load index of 1×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-7} , the optimal weight index predicted by the manual procedure diverges from the result obtained using MATLAB, before converging between a load index of 1×10^{-7} and 1×10^{-6} .

On close examination of the dominant failure combination from the manual procedure, it shows that for load indices below 7.6×10^{-8} , combination FC-FW-IB-CB is the dominant failure mode combination, while combination FC-IB-CY-CB is dominant for load indices greater than and equal to 7.6×10^{-8} .

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